

Minutes EB24-02
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
8 April 2024 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair
Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio

Apology

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair, Reconciliation Commission
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1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

Session at the ASM meeting.

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

Action items from previous meeting

1. KK to follow-up on the NSF's RCN and ICB funding.

Will follow-up on this matter in May

2. FW and LMR to look for Chinese funding opportunities.

A workshop similar to what was proposed for ISME will be presented in October in China. The assistance of a post-doc from the group of FW will also be investigated.

3. PH to investigate the possibility of continued funding from ISME for work on the registry.

PH will confirm with Linda Scholten (ISME Executive Director) but understanding is that funding for 2024 will be at the same levels as in 2023.

4. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.

Done

5. BW to manage the compilation a formal report on the activities of the SeqCode and submit it to the ISME Executive. Publication in ISME Communications to be investigated.

BW is still waiting for summary reports

6. IS, LMR, KK and MC to provide a short summary of their activities for the SeqCode report by 1 March 2023.

IS provided report. LMR, KK and MC to provide report by 30 April.

7. FV and LMR to liaise with the ISME office to prepare the ballot for the proposed changes to the SeqCode.

Voting is delayed due to the workload of the ISME office. An alternative will be discussed.

8. FV to alert the SeqCode Community of the opportunity to vote.

Ongoing

9. FV and LMR to compile the results of the ballot and share it with the EB.

Ongoing

10. MC and LMR to investigate the possibility of linking the SeqCode registry to relevant entries on NCBI.

Some entries are already linked to the SeqCode. This was possibly done by the authors who submitted the genomes. LMR to make a formal request via PubMed LinkOut.

11. FV to share the SeqCode prize entries with EB members to evaluate the entries and make the final decision.

Community was informed that Dr Diego Jimenez from KAUST, Saudi Arabia won the prize.

12. EB members to provide their comments on the Arahal et al. proposal for discussion at the next EB meeting.

Response discussed during the meeting. See below

13. MC to contact a candidate for community panel proposed by FW and submit the roundtable proposal for ISME19.

Done. Currently waiting for the outcome of the application.

14. Redacted

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

Waiting for the assistance from the ISME office to launch ballot on amending SeqCode. If they cannot assist by the end of April due to their involvement in organising ISME19, FV will send out the ballots directly via email. Voting will be open for 1 month. Results will be compiled and shared by FV and LMR.

Standards Working Group

No new issues to report.

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

At present 268 names have been validated and another 249 have been endorsed.

Several people have joined the curation team. The eighth member to join is Prof Giovanna Felis, University of Verona, Italy who will assist with the nomenclature reviews. LMR and BW to discuss some formal acknowledgement for the efforts of the curation team.

The Neo-Latin department of the University of Innsbruck has expressed interest in creating an online session to expose the systematic community to the basic principles of naming using Latin. LMR and FV will discuss the possibility to present this as a BISMIS Live workshop with Kamlesh Jangid.

Reconciliation Commission

The issue of how to validate the name of a genus as part of a later publication was discussed. The EB decided to recommend the optional inclusion of the original (not valid) publication in the formal name citation, and the listing of that publication in the SeqCode Registry entry. The recommended citation should be in parenthesis before the valid publication reference, and preceded by the "ex" particle. These recommendations refer only to the citation of names after valid publication. These changes are to be implemented in the SeqCode Registry as soon as possible.

5. Discussion of Arahall et al. proposed amendments to the ICNP

BW prepared a document outlining the concerns related to the Arahall et al. proposal. The EB supported the views expressed and discussed how this information should be shared with the wider community. After finalising the document BW will post these comments on the ICSP Slack channel. BW will also circulate it among members of the SeqCode Committee and provide a Google sheet that people could use to indicate that they are willing to support this document as signatories. This data could also be shared with the wider community (e.g original webinar attendees)

6. Conference and Meeting Updates

KK has shared the description for the function at ASM Microbe 2024, Atlanta, USA on Friday 14 June.

EB members are encouraged to list SeqCode presentations and share material linked to these presentations on the shared drive.

New action items

1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.
2. LMR to make a formal request via PubMed LinkOut for SeqCode validated names to be linked with the registry.
3. LMR and BW to discuss some formal acknowledgement for the efforts of the curation team.
4. LMR and FV to contact Kamlesh Jangid to enquire if the proposed session by the Neo-Latin department could be accommodated on BISMis Live.
5. KK to submit the description of the proposed SeqCode function at ASM Microbe 2024.
6. BW will post the comments on the Arahall et al. proposal on the ICSP Slack channel.
7. BW to circulate the comments on the Arahall et al. proposal among members of the SeqCode Committee and provide a Google sheet that people could use to indicate that they are willing to support this document as signatories.

Ongoing action items

1. KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding.
2. PH to confirm the SeqCode funding from ISME for 2024 with Linda Scholten.
3. BW to manage the compilation a formal report on the activities of the SeqCode and submit it to the ISME Executive. Publication in ISME Communications to be investigated.
4. LMR, KK and MC to provide a short summary of their activities for the SeqCode report by 30 April 2024
5. FV and LMR to liaise with the ISME office to prepare the ballot for the proposed changes to the SeqCode.
6. FV to alert the SeqCode Community of the opportunity to vote for the amendment of the SeqCode.
7. FV and LMR to compile the results of the ballot and share it with the EB.

Minutes prepared by FV: 9 April 2024

Approved: 24 April 2024